

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF USING SYNONYMS IN DISCOURSE

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Annotation: The importance of synonyms in improving writing is examined in this article. It provides helpful advice and real-world examples to enable writers to use synonyms for clarity and variety of expression. By emphasizing nuance, it enables authors to improve their writing and connect with a range of readers.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada sinonimlarning ahamiyati yozma va og'izaki nutqdagi tahlil qiladi. Yozma nutqda real matnlar va maqolalardan olingan parchalar tahlili asnosida o'rganiladi. U yozuvchilarga ravshanlik va ifoda xilma-xilligi uchun sinonimlardan foydalanish imkonini beradigan foydali maslahatlar va real misollarni taqdim etadi. Nuancen ta'kidlab, u mualliflarga o'z yozuvlarini yaxshilash va bir qator o'quvchilar bilan bog'lanish imkonini beradi.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается значение синонимов в совершенствовании письма. Он содержит полезные советы и примеры из реальной жизни, которые помогут авторам использовать синонимы для ясности и разнообразия выражения. Подчеркивая нюансы, это позволяет авторам улучшить свое письмо и связаться с широким кругом читателей.

Key words: synonymy, near-synonymy, writing, nuance.

INTRODUCTION

Effective writing relies on the careful choice of words. In this case, synonyms can be a handy tool for writers. They help make writing clearer and more interesting. Making extensive use of lexical variety, synonymous expressions, and synonyms keep the reader engaged in your writing. Changing a word to something similar, possibly even more precise, can help you better express your ideas. Using synonyms enhances the vividness of writing and helps the reader form a more compelling mental image [3].

Synonym is one of two or more words or expressions of the same language that have the same or nearly the same meaning in some or all senses [4]. Synonyms can be any part of speech, as long as both words belong to the same part of speech. Examples:

- noun: drink and beverage
- verb: buy and purchase
- adjective: big and large
- adverb: quickly and speedily
- preposition: on and upon [6]

Although synonyms are useful tools for improving communication and enriching language, it's important to understand that not all synonyms are interchangeable. Three distinct groups of synonyms are identified by Alan Cruise in his book [1]: absolute synonyms, propositional synonyms, and near-synonyms. It is essential to comprehend the distinctions between these groups in order to communicate and use language effectively.

When two words or phrases have exactly the same meaning and can be used interchangeably without changing interpretation, it's a rare occurrence in language that they are absolute synonyms. These occurrences are comparatively rare and are frequently observed in specialized or technical fields.

Conversely, propositional synonyms have similar meanings in certain propositions or contexts but may have different meanings in other contexts. They give authors ways to convey the same idea or claim in slightly different ways, satisfying various stylistic nuances or preferences.

Near-synonyms are words or phrases with similar meanings but may differ in nuances, connotations, or usage contexts. They are arguably the most common type encountered in everyday language. Although they have a similar meaning, near-synonyms are not always the same and can be preferred by different speakers or in different situations.

NEAR-SYNONYMY

Many people claim that writing in English is a difficult process since this language has lots of equivalent words. They are really eager to replace almost every word by using synonymy, and most of them make mistakes in near-synonymy.

Sometimes words might seem to have exactly the same meaning, but when you analyze them carefully, it becomes obvious that there are some nuances in meaning, connotation and usage, and they cannot be always replaced with each other. For instance, talk and speak. They are near-synonyms, because they both mean to communicate orally; however, they cannot be fully exchangeable in a certain context: talk generally refers to the act of communicating often in a casual or informal manner; whereas speak can imply a more formal or intentional manner of communication compared to "talk"[5].

Other most common examples are pretty and handsome, which are two distinct forms with the same meaning. Nonetheless, pretty usually collocates with women, and handsome is associated with men [3].

Analyzing the partly synonymy here some examples to be discussed:

Below are more examples, but each pair of sentences contain common mistakes in near-synonymy made by English learners and their analyses.

1. Correct: "She *talked* to her friend for hours." - Here, "*talked*" is used appropriately to describe a conversation between two people.

Incorrect: "She *spoke* to her friend for hours."- In this sentence, "*spoke*" is a near-synonym of "talked," but it's used incorrectly. While "*spoke*" is a synonym of "*talked*" in many contexts, it doesn't convey the informal and casual nature of the conversation as effectively.

2. Correct: "The team *focused on* improving their performance." - In this sentence, "*focused*" is used correctly to indicate the team's concentration on a specific task or goal.

Incorrect: "The team concentrated on improving their performance." - While "*concentrated*" is a near-synonym of "*focused*," it's not the best choice in this context. "Concentrated" typically implies a more intense or deliberate focus, which may not be the intended meaning here.

3. Correct: "They *discussed* the project during the meeting." - "*Discussed*" is correctly used here to describe a conversation or exchange of ideas about the project.

Incorrect: "They *chatted* about the project during the meeting." - While "*chatted*" is a near-synonym of "*discussed*," it may not convey the level of seriousness or depth of conversation that "*discussed*" does. It's more casual and informal.

4. Correct: "She *began* her presentation with an overview of the topic." - "*Began*" is the appropriate word here to indicate the start of her presentation. *Begun* =start, *Launch* can be absolute synonymy in cases.

Incorrect: "She *commenced* her presentation with an overview of the topic." - "*Commenced*" is a near-synonym of "*began*," but it's not the best choice in this context. "*Commenced*" is more formal and less commonly used in everyday language.

DISCUSSION

To support the idea being discussed in this article, we analyze the synonyms of a passage of another article taken from New Scientist magazine [2]:

“An experimental treatment for Alzheimer's disease involving sounds and flickering lights has shown promise in mice and people. Now, research suggests the novel approach ramps up our brain's waste disposal networks.

A new explanation has emerged for why an experimental treatment for Alzheimer's disease involving sounds and flickering lights may help slow cognitive decline. The frequencies involved seem to ramp up the brain's waste disposal networks, which boosts the clearance of beta-amyloid and other toxic proteins that contribute to memory and concentration problems.

“Once we understand the mechanism, we can probably figure out how to further optimize this whole concept and improve the efficacy,” says Li-Huei Tsai at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology.

The treatment involves exposing people to lights flickering at a frequency of 40 times a second, or 40 hertz, and a low-pitched sound, also at 40 Hz. Typically, the stimulation is given for an hour a day.

Key to the novel approach is that large networks of brain cells naturally fire in sync with each other at different frequencies – known as brainwaves. Brainwaves of around 40 Hz are often seen when people are concentrating and when they are forming or accessing memories.

As it was known that visual or auditory stimulation at a certain frequency can boost brainwaves at that same frequency, in 2016, Tsai’s team decided to investigate if 40 Hz stimulation might boost cognitive abilities in people with Alzheimer’s”.

The following are **near-synonyms** in the given text:

1. The terms "treatment" and "approach" denote different approaches to treating Alzheimer's disease, but they have similar meanings. Whereas "approach" denotes a more comprehensive strategy or methodology, "treatment" denotes a medical procedure.

2. Emerged and suggested: These terms both allude to something that is either being put forth or that has come to light. The word "emerged" implies something coming to light or becoming apparent, whereas the word "suggested" suggests an idea being advanced or suggested.

3. Cognitive abilities and concentration: Both terms refer to mental powers or capacities. Concentration is the capacity to concentrate, whereas cognitive abilities are a wider range of mental functions such as memory, attention, and problem solving.

4. Optimize and improve: Although they are not exactly the same, both terms refer to the process of making something more efficient or better. While "improve" denotes raising general quality or functionality, "optimize" suggests maximizing efficiency or performance.

5. Both frequency and Hz (hertz) describe the rate at which an event occurs or repeats. "Hz" stands for cycles per second, which is the specific unit of measurement for frequency; "frequency" is a more general term.

These near-synonyms offer small differences in emphasis or meaning, enabling a more complex way to express concepts in the text.

CONCLUSION

In summary, this article highlights the importance of using different words that have similar meanings in writing. By exploring how synonyms can make writing clearer and more interesting, it provides practical tips for writers to enhance their vocabulary and expression. Understanding the nuances between words helps writers convey their ideas more effectively and engage with a wider audience. As writers continue to practice and apply these techniques, they can improve their writing skills and create more compelling content.

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